

Dorsal Hand Veins in Oman and Their Added Value in Multimodal Biometrics: A Pilot Study with Airport Feasibility Benchmarking

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Introduction

Dorsal veins form a network on the dorsum of the hand. The dorsal venous arch drains into the basilic and cephalic veins. Dorsal veins have shown unique biometric potential. As such, this study aimed to characterize dorsal metacarpal vein prominence in an Omani cohort and to compare, using international benchmarks, face+fingerprint verification versus face+fingerprint+dorsal hand veins.

Materials and Methods

A descriptive observational study analyzed 99 participants (99 pairs of hands). Dorsal hand veins were captured using the Vein Scanner mobile application supported by 48/64-MP photography, fixed tripod (reflection mode), enhanced illumination, and image processing. Images were excluded if poor quality, veins not visible, or obstructed. An airport feasibility extension (Muscat International Airport) enrolled two operational groups (n=50 each): (i) face+fingerprint+dorsal veins and (ii) face+fingerprint.

Results

In the pilot dataset, 180/190 hands (94.7%) exhibited prominent veins suitable for assessment. The second dorsal metacarpal vein was most frequently prominent (49.47%), followed by the third (35.79%), fourth (7.89%), and first (1.58%). For performance comparison, our study benchmarks report face+fingerprint accuracy of 90.8% to 99.43%. When incorporating a vascular modality (e.g., fingerprint+finger-vein fusion), reported recognition/identification performance is typically 98.74% to 99.62%, supporting improved accuracy and robustness when vein information is added to existing modalities.

Conclusion

Dorsal hand veins were visible in most analyzed hands, with consistent dominance of the second dorsal metacarpal vein. Our study supports evaluating face+fingerprint+dorsal veins as potentially more accurate and robust than face+fingerprint in operational settings.

Keywords

Dorsal Hand Veins, Biometrics, Branching Patterns, Vein Prominence, Omani Population, Vein Biometrics.